

EFFECT OF COLONIZATION OF THE FUNGUS *BEAUVERIA BASSIANA* ON SALICYLIC ACID CONTENT AND POPULATION OF *BEMISIA TABACI* ON RED CHILI (*CAPSICUM ANNUUM* L.)

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Abstract:

The study aimed to determine the effect of *Beauveria bassiana* inoculation on the distribution of endophytic *B. bassiana* fungus colonization on plants, salicylic acid content, and population of *B. tabaci* insects on chili plants. The fungal isolates used were endophytic fungi from wheat (TD312), cacao (KT211), coffee plants (APKo), and entomopathogenic fungi from the insect *Nilaparvata oratorius* (BbWS). The inoculation technique was carried out by soaking the chili seeds for 6 (six) hours. The research was conducted at the Biological Control Laboratory and Wire House, Faculty of Agriculture, Andalas University from June to October 2021. The design used was a completely randomized design. Observation variables included the distribution of *B. bassiana* fungus colonization on the roots, stems, and leaves of chili peppers. analyzed the content of salicylic acid and observed the population of *Bemisia tabaci* on plants aged 7 to 63 days after transplanting. The results showed that all tested *B. bassiana* isolates were able to colonize the roots, stems, and leaves of chili peppers. The TD312 isolate produced the highest endophytic colonization and was found in leaves (53.33%), the lowest *B. tabaci* population was obtained from the treatment of *B. bassiana* \BbWS isolates (9.00%). The highest content of salicylic acid was found in isolate TD312 at 15,427 ppm and the lowest was in the treatment of BbWS isolate at 9.298 ppm and control at 6.62 ppm. The overall results showed that inoculation of the endophytic entomopathogenic *B. bassiana* fungus was able to colonize plants and increase the salicylic acid content of chili plants and affect the population of *B. tabaci*.

Keywords: *Bauveria bassiana*, *Bemisia tabaci*, koloniassi, *Bauveria bassiana*, red chili pepper, Salicylic.

Introduction

Red chili (*Capsicum annuum* L.) is a horticultural crop that has high economic value, used for household needs, as well as in the food industry. Some of the obstacles that affect the quality of red chili so that production every year often fluctuates is the attack of plant-disturbing organisms. The control of pests on chili plants by farmers is still focused on using chemical pesticides because they are considered the easiest and most effective. One of the pests that attack chili plants is the aphid *Bemisia tabaci*. *B. tabaci* is a polyphagous insect, widely distributed in subtropical and tropical areas (Delatte et al. 2005). To overcome this pest, farmers generally use chemical pesticides. The unwise use of chemical pesticides is detrimental to humans and agroecosystems, so it is necessary to find safe and environmentally friendly controls, one of which is by using entomopathogenic fungi and endophytic fungi. The entomopathogenic fungus *B. bassiana* has the potential to control this mealybug on chili plants (Barra-Bucarei and Ortiz 2020). Endophytic fungi are microorganisms that colonize plant tissues, namely on roots, stems, leaves, flowers or seeds without harming the host (Yadav 2018). Endophytic fungi are useful for maintaining plant resistance to abiotic stress factors

such as increasing drought tolerance, plant disturbances at high and low temperatures, low pH environmental conditions, high salinity and describing if there are heavy metals in the soil (Lombard and Place 2015). Endophytic fungi are capable of producing the same bioactive compounds and secondary metabolites as their host plants. The bioactive compounds produced by endophytic fungi are also useful in the agricultural, pharmaceutical and medical industries (Egbuna et al. 2019).

Microorganisms can be used to stimulate plant processes, increase growth through nutrient absorption, increase insect and disease resistance, plant quality, and efficiency. Several previous studies have shown that endophytic fungi are able to protect their host plants against plant pathogens and herbivorous insects (Vega et al. 2008)(Jaber and Araj 2018)(Russo et al. 2019), stated that *B. bassiana* was able to colonize soybean plants through seed soaking. The results of Jaber and Enkerli's research (2016), stated that the fungus *B. bassiana* was able to colonize and increase the growth of *Vicia faba* plants through seed soaking applications. (Powell et al. 2009) reported that endophytic fungi were able to colonize chili plants both during the seedling, flowering, and fruiting phases with isolation frequencies of 12.21 and 67%, respectively. Furthermore, (Trizelia et al. 2020) stated that colonization of endophytic fungi was more commonly found on the leaves of chili plants, the ability of plant colonization was strongly influenced by plant physiology. This study aimed to determine the effect of *B. bassiana* inoculation on the distribution of endophytic fungus *B. bassiana* colonization on chili plants and to see the effect of fungal colonization on the content of salicylic acid which can induce plant resistance to *Bemisia tabaci*.

Materials and methods

Materials

The research included: 1. inoculation of the fungus *B. bassiana* on the distribution of endophytic colonization of *B. bassiana* on chili plants; Analyzing the content of salicylic acid based on the effect of colonization of the fungus *B. bassiana* and observations of the population of *B. tabaci* on chili plants.

Colonization of *B. bassiana* in chili plants

The *B. bassiana* fungus used in this study is a collection of the Laboratory of Biological Control, Faculty of Agriculture, Andalas University, namely the endophytic *B. bassiana* fungus derived from the Wheat plant (TD312), the Coffee plant (APKo), from the Cocoa plant (KT211) and the fungus *B. bassiana* entomopathogen from the insect *Walang Sangit* (*Nilaparvata oratorius*) BbWS. The ability to colonize the fungus *B. bassiana* on chili plants was observed in plants aged 35 days after inoculation of the fungus *B. bassiana*. Inoculation of the *B. bassiana* fungus was carried out by soaking the seeds for 6 hours, then chili seeds were planted until 35 days after inoculation, which was the result of a previous study modified from the research of (Qayyum et al. 2015).

Plants aged 35 days were removed and cleaned with running water, then the roots, stems, and leaves of chili plants were cut into small pieces with a size of 1 cm, then sterilized using 70%

alcohol for 1 minute, followed by 1% NaOCl for 1 minute, then washed with sterile distilled water. and dried in a laminar airflow cabinet (Tefera and Vidal 2009). Roots, stems, and leaves were grown in selective oatmeal agar (OA) medium in Petri dishes, and each petri dish contained 5 pieces of roots, stems, and leaves, each treatment was repeated three times. Colonization observations were carried out after 10 days to see the presence of *B. bassiana* in the presence of mycelium or conidia coming out of the ends of the plant tissue. The percentage of colonization was calculated based on the number of pieces of plant parts that showed fungal growth compared to all pieces of plant parts. The design used was a non-factorial completely randomized design. Data analysis was carried out using variance and if there was a significant effect between treatments, it was continued with Duncan's test at an error rate of 5%. Calculation of colonization of the fungus *B. bassiana* using the formula:

$$PK = \frac{\sum n}{N} \times 100\%$$

PK : Percentage of colonization

n : Number of sample pieces of plants infected with the fungus *B. bassiana*

N : Number of plant sample pieces observed

Effect of colonization of the fungus *B. bassiana* on *Bemisia tabaci*

The research was conducted at the wire house of the Faculty of Agriculture, Andalas University from June to September 2021. The presence of *B. tabaci* in chili plants was carried out at a vegetative age. Observation and calculation of the population of *B. tabaci* present on plant leaves at 7-day intervals starting at 7 days of observation until 63 days after transplanting. by counting the number of imago present in all sample plants. The total population of *B. tabaci* that was present in each treatment (isolate) tested showed an indication of the influence of colonization and salicylic acid compounds that affected the presence of *B. tabaci* in chili plants. Observational data obtained using variance, if the resultant data between treatments has a significant effect, then it is continued with Duncan's test at an error level of 5%.

Analysis of salicylic acid content

To determine the effect of endophytic *B. bassiana* inoculation on the content of salicylic acid, the leaves of chili plants were vegetatively aged 56 days, by combining 5 plants, for each treatment. Extraction and quantification of salicylic acid were carried out by a modified method (Corina Vlot, Dempsey, and Klessig 2009). A total of 5 grams of chili plant leaves were crushed, then extracted with methanol, then the extract was centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 15 minutes, then the supernatant was taken. The content of salicylic acid was analyzed by High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). 5 l of methanol extract of tomato plant leaves was injected into the C18 column (4.6 ID x 250 mm; Lichrospher 100 Rp. 18, sodium acetate, pH 4.5). Salicylic acid was eluted isocratically 15 min after injection and detected by fluorescence (254 nm excitation; 402 nm emission). The concentration of salicylic acid was measured using a linear range from a calibration standard containing 0-1.3 mg/50 ml of salicylic acid (Sigma-Aldrich, St.Louis). The concentration of salicylic acid is expressed in micrograms per gram of fresh weight. Salicylic acid content is expressed in ppm.

B. bassiana Fungus Colonization on Chili Plants

The results of the inoculation test of *B. bassiana* fungus isolates were able to colonize the roots, stems and leaves of chili plants. The effect of *B. bassiana* inoculation on the distribution of endophytic colonization in chili plants can be seen in Table 1 and Graph.1.

Table 1: Distribution of *B. bassiana* Fungal Colonization

Isolate	Colony Distributiun (%)		
	Root	Stem	Leaf
Control	0.0b	0.0c	0.0c
KT211	6.67ab	26.67ab	26.67b
APKo	13.3ab	13.3b	26.67b
TD312	26.67a	40.0a	53.33a
BbWS	13.33ab	33.33a	33.33ab

The highest endophytic colonization was found in leaf tissue in the treatment of TD312 isolate (53.3%) followed by BbWS isolate at 33.33%. The highest percentage of endophytic colonization on stems was also found in TD312 isolates at 40.0% and not significantly different from BbWS isolates (33.33%), as well as in roots, the highest endophytic colonization was found in TD312 isolates and not significantly different from BbWS isolates (13.33%). There was a difference in the percentage of colonization on chili leaves that was not significant between the two isolates TD312 and BbWS, but significantly different between isolates KT211 and isolate APKo. There was no statistical difference between the kT211 isolates and APKo isolates. Overall, the results of artificial inoculation treatment showed that the tested *B. bassiana* fungus was able to settle as endophytes on the roots, stems, and leaves of chili plants. This is evidenced by the presence of mycelium growth on isolated plant parts which were identified macroscopically and microscopically. When related to the effect of *B. bassiana* inoculation on the distribution of endophytic colonization in chili plants, it was seen that all isolates of the endophytic fungus TD312, KT211, APKo, and the entomopathogenic fungus BbWS tested were able to settle as endophytes on the roots, stems, and leaves of chili peppers. The ability and spread of the fungus *B. bassiana* to become endophytes is to establish a localization of infection on the roots, stems, and leaves that spreads using spores (Faeth and Fagan 2002).

Furthermore, (Sobowale 2011), explained the ability of good endophytic fungi, namely having the ability to develop from the starting point of inoculation to all other host tissues because of the aggressive nature associated with the growth rate of the fungus to colonize the available space. In addition to being able to colonize the host, the spread of endophytes must also be able to be distributed throughout the plant tissue. This trait or character is known as the aggressive capacity of the fungus.

Figure 1: Graph of colonization distribution on chili plants on various isolates.

The potential of the fungus *Beauveria bassiana* in colonizing plant tissue is influenced by the strain of the fungus itself (Zhang 2014). The results of the research by (Rodriguez et al. 2009), treatment of *B. bassiana* fungus inoculation with seed immersion technique, conidia will enter at the same time as the imbibition process by diffusion and penetrate the seed wall. Furthermore, (Powell et al. 2009), stated that the spread of the fungus *B. bassiana* was evenly distributed due to passive transmission which caused random diffusion in plant tissues. The results of further research conducted by (Russo et al. 2019), *B. bassiana* was able to colonize soybean plants through seed soaking. The results of the study by (Gao, Dai, and Liu 2010) explained that fungi can persist as endophytes in plant tissues influenced by plant factors and the fungus itself, such as differences in fungal strains/isolates, fungal physiology, plant physiology, and plant conditions (Rivas-Franco et al. 2020). (Jaber and Alananbeh 2018) explained that the fungus *B. bassiana* was able to colonize and increase the growth of *Vicia faba* plants through seed soaking applications. In leaves, the highest percentage of endophytic fungi found is endemic in parenchyma, xylem, and phloem tissues (Vega et al. 2008). The ability of plant colonization by the fungus *B. bassiana* is strongly influenced by plant physiological factors (Trizelia et al. 2020).

Effect of colonization of *B. bassiana* on the population of *B. tabaci*

Observations on the effect of *B. bassiana* colonization on the presence of *Bemisia tabaci* can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2: Population of *B. tabaci* on Observation 7- 63 days after planting

Isolate	Average Population of <i>B. tabaci</i> on Observation days after planting (day)								
	7	14	21	28	35	42	49	56	63
Control	4.11a	3.88a	5.66a	6.44a	7.11a	8.00a	8.33a	9.11a	9.22a
KT211	2.88b	2.44b	3.55bc	4.22bc	3.55c	4.00b	3.66b	2.88b	2.88b
APKo	2.44b	2.22b	4.00b	5.00b	4.44b	3.88b	3.55b	2.44bc	2.22c
TD312	1.66c	1.88b	3.55bc	4.00c	3.33c	2.77c	3.00b	2.33bc	2.00c
BbWS	1.33c	1.00c	2.88c	3.66c	3.00c	2.55c	2.55b	1.88c	1.88c

Observations on the presence of imago *B. tabaci* were carried out at the age of 7 days to 63 days after planting, i.e. every 7 day interval after transplanting. The population of *B. tabaci* that appeared on plants during the observation seemed to fluctuate. Imago *B. tabaci* from all observations for 7 to 63 days after planting, the lowest population mean was seen in BbWS isolates and the highest population was found in controls. The average fluctuation of the imago population present at each observation can be seen in the graph. 1.

Figure 2: The graph of average population of *B. tabaci* at observations was 7 days to 63 days.

The imago population present in each observation fluctuated as shown in figure 2. The average percentage of *B. tabaci* imago present at the observation 7 days after planting (7days) was low as well as at the observation 14 days after planting, the lowest population was in BbWS isolates and the highest was in the control. At 14 days after observation, there was a significant difference in the percentage of *B. tabaci* imago between the entomopathogenic fungus BbWS and the three endophytic fungi isolates TD312, APKo, and KT211. The increase in *B. tabaci* imago statistically began to be seen at observations 21 and 28 days after planting and there was a statistical decrease from the age of observation 35 to 63 days after planting. The increasing age of chili plants can affect the presence of *B. tabaci* populations that come to plants. The *B.*

tabaci population contained in BbWS isolates was the lowest *B. tabaci* population compared to the other three *B. bassiana* endophytic isolates. Endophytic entomopathogenic fungi isolates showed a lower population of *B. tabaci* than endophytic fungi isolates TD312, KT211, and APKo.

The presence of endophytic colonization on chili plant leaves from the tested fungal isolates could affect the presence of *B. tabaci* imago on plants. Research by (Jaber and Araj 2018), explained that endophytic colonization of *B. bassiana* and *Metarrhizium brunneum* fungi was able to settle as endophytes on sweet pepper plants, and the highest colonization was found in leaves and effectively reduced *Myzus persicae* populations through seed soaking applications. Endophytic fungi inoculation through seed immersion technique provides hope and a good control strategy for pest control in plants. The effect of *B. bassiana* inoculation on plant colonization and salicylic acid content and the presence of *B. tabaci* can be seen in Table 3.

Figure 3: Morphology of *B.basiana* isolate on SDAY media : a. BbWS, b. APKo, c. KT211,d.TD312

B. bassiana inoculation treatment through seed soaking was able to colonize the entire network of roots, stems, and chili plants. The effect of colonization of endophytic fungi physiologically affects the salicylic acid content of chili plants, this can be seen from the presence and population of *B. tabaci* insects on chili plants. The average content of salicylic acid in chili plant leaves and its effect on the population of *B. tabaci* can be seen in the table. 3.

Table 3: Salicylic Acid Content

	Colony distribution	Salicylic Acid content
Isolate	(%)	(ppm)
Control	0	6.62e
KT211	26.67	12.05c
APKo	26.6	13.51b
TD312	53.33	15.42a
BbWS	33.33	9.29d

In Table.3. it can be seen, that the highest content of salicylic acid was found in isolates TD312 (15,427) and statistically significant difference in the content of salicylic acid in the treatment of isolates KT211, APKo isolates, and BbWS isolates as well as in the control. Although the salicylic acid content in BbWS isolates was lower than that of TD312 and KT21 and APKo isolates, the population of *B. tabaci* present in chili plants was lower than that of *B. tabaci* in KT211, APKo, and different. not significant with TD312 isolate. The BbWS isolate used was derived from the entomopathogenic fungus *B. bassiana* from the insect *Nilaparvata oratorius*. *B. bassiana* inoculation can affect the physiological and biochemical responses of plants by increasing the production of chemical compounds such as ethylene, chitinase, phytoalexin alkaloids, jasmonic acid, and salicylic acid (Schweiger et al. 2014). The amount of salicylic acid content can depend on the interaction between the endophytic fungal life cycle, plant growth, and symbiotic associations of specific species and/or plant tissues (Lombard and Place 2015).

Beneficial microorganisms can produce changes in plant immune responses (Pieterse et al. 2014) are known as biotrophic pathogens and activate the salicylic acid pathway, in response microorganisms produce specific enzymes that suppress the salicylic acid pathway to colonize root tissue and form symbiotic bonds (Fig. (Telfer 2014). According to (Gao, Dai, and Liu 2010), endophytic fungi protect plants against pathogens or insects by inhibiting indirectly through endophytic stimulation of plants in the formation of secondary metabolites such as salicylic acid, jasmonic acid, and ethylene. Furthermore, (Rivas-Franco et al. 2020) stated that corn plants colonized by the fungus *Metarrhizium anisopliae* A1080 had higher salicylic and jasmonic acid content. Salicylic acid has an important role in plant defense against aphids by producing antibiotics or repellents that can affect aphid infestation patterns on tomato plants (Moran and Thompson 2001).

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research conducted, it can be concluded that the inoculation of endophytic *B. bassiana* and *B. bassiana* entomopathogenic fungi tested were able to persist as endophytes and colonize chili plants on the roots, stems, and leaves of chili plants. The highest endophytic fungal colonization was found in chili plant leaves from TD312 isolate and not significantly different from BbWS isolate. Colonization of the fungus *B. bassiana* affected the

population of *B. tabaci* and the content of salicylic acid in chili plants. The lowest population of *B. tabaci* was found in the treatment of the fungus BbWS isolate from the entomopathogenic fungus *Nilaparvata oratorius*. of 9.00%. The colonization effect of endophytic fungi can also increase the content of salicylic acid in plants. The isolate of the fungus *B. bassiana* which had the highest content of salicylic acid was found in isolates from wheat plant TD312, which was 15,427 ppm. The effect of endophytic colonization of the fungus *B. bassiana* on chili plants can increase the content of salicylic acid and can induce resistance of chili plants to *B. tabaci*. Endophytic fungi inoculation through seed immersion technique provides hope and a good control strategy for pest control in plants.

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